

ISic1374

I.Sicily inscription 1374

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo S. Nicolai

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140879

1. [— — — — — ὁ τῆς μακαρία]ς μνήμης
2. [— — — — — — — — — — —]ΚΑΛΟΥΒΙΟΥ
3. [— — — — — — — — — — —]ΥΣΤΟΣΠΙΣΤΟΣ
4. [— — — ἠγόρασα τὸν τόπον] παρὰ Ἄλε-
5. [ξάνδρου καὶ — — — τῶν εὐ]μοιρε[ιτ]ῶν.
- 6.

Edition: PHI140880

1. [ἐνθάδε κατάκεινται]
2. [ἠ μακαρία]ς μνήμης
3. [ἠ δεῖνα διὰ] καλοῦ βίου
4. [ἐλθοῦσα κ(αὶ) Ἰο]ῦστος πιστός·
5. [ἠγόρασαν] παρὰ Ἄλε-
6. [ξάνδρου. εὐ]μοιρε[ιτ]ῶν.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0555 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 4.9498

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